

The SYNTHEMA project continues to make significant strides in advancing synthetic data generation and federated learning technologies in the healthcare sector. At the **European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) 2024**, SYNTHEMA's involvement under the HealthData4EU cluster further cemented its role as a key player in addressing critical challenges related to rare disease data. Through engaging presentations, interactive panels, and collaborations with fellow projects such as SECURED and AISym4MED, SYNTHEMA showcased its cutting-edge solutions that are transforming how healthcare data is generated, shared, and protected across Europe.

This newsletter highlights SYNTHEMA's impactful presence at EBDVF 2024, its contribution to important discussions on synthetic data and federated learning, and its role in fostering meaningful partnerships with stakeholders from the AI, data, and healthcare sectors. It also covers SYNTHEMA's participation at the ASCAT 2024 conference in London, where the project was showcased alongside Genomed4ALL, further reinforcing its importance in precision medicine and rare hematological disease research.

SYNTHEMA at EBDVF 2024: Advancing Synthetic Data Generation in Health with HealthData4EU Cluster

At the 2024 European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF), SYNTHEMA made a prominent impact through its participation in a joint session under the HealthData4EU cluster, alongside project partners SECURED EU and AISym4MED. Held in Budapest from October 2-4, the event brought together researchers, industry leaders, and policymakers from across Europe and beyond. The session, titled "**Showcasing Innovative Research for Synthetic Data Generation from the HealthData4EU Cluster Projects**", took place on October 2 and spotlighted cutting-edge developments in synthetic data technologies for healthcare.

SYNTHEMA's involvement extended further with a significant presence in the "**Synthetic Data in Healthcare**" panel discussion, led by the BDVA Health Task Force. In this session, SYNTHEMA researchers joined a multidisciplinary panel to explore how synthetic data is reshaping patient care, driving research, and ensuring data privacy. In addition to these key presentations, SYNTHEMA, together with SECURED and AISym4MED, co-hosted a joint booth at the event. This booth provided a valuable platform for one-on-one discussions with stakeholders from the healthcare, AI, and data sectors, facilitating direct engagement with industry experts and policymakers. These interactions allowed the SYNTHEMA team to exchange insights, build connections, and discuss the transformative potential of their work with key decision-makers.

Collaboration with AISym4MED and SECURED

The session, "Showcasing Innovative Research for Synthetic Data Generation from the HealthData4EU Cluster Projects", moderated by **Serena Battaglia**, Project Adviser at the **European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)**, included contributions from the SYNTHEMA, AISym4MED and SECURED projects.

- **SYNTHEMA's** presentation, led by **Dr. Sofia Tsekeridou of Netcompany-Intrasoft**, focused on addressing the critical issue of data scarcity in rare diseases. Through federated learning, SYNTHEMA's innovative platform securely accesses scarce health data from dispersed clinical sites, enabling the generation of synthetic data in a privacy-preserving manner. Dr. Tsekeridou emphasized SYNTHEMA's approach to federated training across unconnected clinical sites, which reduces biases and improves the quality of synthetic data, particularly for rare hematological diseases. This solution paves the way for the creation of virtual patients to enhance diagnostics, treatment assessments, and health outcome predictions.
- **AISym4MED**, presented by Dr. Luis Rosado of Fraunhofer AICOS, focused on evaluating the quality of synthetic medical data through a new open-source

library for data auditing. This tool aims to ensure the realism and usefulness of synthetic data in healthcare.

- **SECURED**, led by Dr. Francesco Regazzoni from the University of Amsterdam, explored privacy-preserving technologies in healthcare. Dr. Regazzoni discussed the strengths and limitations of various privacy techniques and their relevance to health applications.

Together, these projects demonstrated the collective strength of the HealthData4EU cluster in advancing secure, privacy-preserving technologies for healthcare data.

Joint Booth and Stakeholder Engagement

SYNTHEMA, SECURED, and AISYM4MED further strengthened their presence at the event with a joint booth. This interactive platform allowed project representatives to engage with a wide array of relevant individuals from the sector. These one-on-one discussions provided an opportunity to dive deeper into the challenges and innovations of synthetic data generation, federated learning, and privacy technologies, fostering valuable connections with experts and decision-makers in healthcare and AI.

Additional Participation: Panel on Synthetic Data in Healthcare

Further highlighting SYNTHEMA's prominence at the event, project partners Sofia Tsekeridou and Mattia Dellean also participated in the session "**Synthetic Data in Healthcare**" later that day. This panel discussion, held from 11:30 to 13:00, featured experts from various disciplines discussing how synthetic data is revolutionizing patient care, research, and data privacy. Moderated by a co-lead of the BDVA Health Track, the session covered both the potential and the ethical challenges of using synthetic data in healthcare.

The second part of the session showcased Hungarian healthcare data projects, examining the growing value of healthcare data, the impact of AI on healthcare, and cybersecurity concerns. The panel provided a comprehensive look at how synthetic data is shaping the future of healthcare, with insights from diverse perspectives across the industry.

SECURED Project Workshop: Synthetic Data Generation for Medical Education

During the insightful presentations from SECURED on synthetic data generation in medical imaging, SYNTHEMA contributed to the workshop on "Synthetic Data Generation for Medical Education" with a presentation by Anna Rizzo, a representative from SYNTHEMA's partner, Datawizard. Rizzo highlighted SYNTHEMA's innovative approach to generating synthetic data for rare diseases, emphasizing the project's potential to revolutionize medical education by providing high-quality synthetic data for training and research. This participation allowed SYNTHEMA to showcase its complementary technologies and methodologies, aligning with the workshop's focus on advancing synthetic data for medical applications.

SYNTHEMA and Genomed4ALL Presented at ASCAT 2024 by ERN-EuroBloodNet

SYNTHEMA partners, representatives from ERN-EuroBloodNet, attended the **19th Annual Scientific Conference of the Academy for Sickle Cell and Thalassemia (ASCAT 2024)** in London, from October 2-5. This event, co-hosted by the British Society of Haematology and the European Hematology Association, offered a platform to explore the latest advancements in haemoglobinopathies, including breakthroughs in diagnosis, treatment, and therapies for Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) and Thalassemia. During ASCAT 2024, SYNTHEMA and its sister project Genomed4ALL were presented in a dedicated session of the conference. Highlighting the importance of precision medicine in treating rare hematological diseases, the projects were introduced in the "ERN-EuroBloodNet SCD Patient Session," coordinated by Mariangela Pellegrini, the Educational & Patients Program Manager of ERN-EuroBloodNet.

The session emphasized the role of SYNTHEMA and Genomed4ALL in advancing synthetic data generation and federated learning technologies, crucial for improving diagnostic tools and treatment options for patients with rare diseases such as SCD. This participation reinforced the collaborative efforts of ERN-EuroBloodNet in supporting these projects, underscoring their importance in advancing healthcare research and patient advocacy within the haemoglobinopathies community.

Stay tuned for more exciting updates from SYNTHEMA as we continue to push the boundaries of synthetic data generation and federated learning in healthcare. With new collaborations and groundbreaking innovations on the horizon, there's much more to come. Follow us for the latest developments and upcoming events!